

Needed: More Responsibility, More Objectivity, Less Bias

Linus Pauling, Ph.D., F.A.P.M.

Linus Pauling was born in Portland, Oregon, February 28, 1901 and was educated in the schools of Condon and Portland. He received his bachelor's degree in 1922 from Oregon State College and his Ph.D. degree in chemistry in 1925 from California Institute of Technology. He was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry for 1954 and the Nobel Prize for Peace for 1962 and has received other awards in the fields of chemistry, mineralogy, biology, medicine and peace. Professor Pauling has been a frequent contributor to IAPM publications and is a member of the Editorial Board of the *JIAM*. He is at present Director of the Institute of Orthomolecular Medicine at Menlo Park, California and Professor of Chemistry at Stanford University.

Dr. A. Hoffer has pointed out that the critics of megavitamin therapy and orthomolecular medicine are willing to advance arguments that favor their stand on the basis of the most flimsy evidence. The editors of newspapers show a shocking lack of responsibility in their willingness to publish thoroughly unreliable statements about vitamins. This irresponsibility has been shown in a flagrant way by the *Chicago Tribune* and by many other newspapers that published an article taken from the *Chicago Tribune*.

The article was published under the title "A New Disease: Overdose of Vitamin C." The article was written by Carol Rasmussen of the *Chicago Tribune*. She said that two persons, a man and his wife, had been sent to a suburban Chicago hospital. They complained of sore gums, loose teeth, aching legs and ease of bruising. In the hospital a nutritionist, Betty Wedman, is quoted as saying that they were suffering from a new disease, overdose of vitamin C, with symptoms similar to those of scurvy, which results from a deficiency of vitamin C.

The two persons are said to have been living on a very unsatisfactory diet, containing essentially no vegetables. They had been taking 1500 or 2000 milligrams of vitamin C for a few months, but, so far as can be told from the article, no other dietary supplements. They were advised to eat a balanced diet. It is not stated in the newspaper articles whether the signs and symptoms of disease then disappeared.

Thousands of people have taken large amounts of vitamin C, between 2 grams and 20 grams a day, for years, without showing any such manifestations of disease as described in this newspaper article. There is no possibility that the reported manifestations were the result of ingesting 1500 or 2000 milligrams of vitamin C per day. The claim that these two persons were suffering from a new disease, overdose of vitamin C, was made by the dietician because of ignorance and irresponsibility. The writer of the article and the editor of the *Chicago Tribune* were irresponsible in not checking carefully before publication of the article.

Another example of irresponsibility involves the claim, made in 1974 by Dr. Victor Herbert and Dr. Elizabeth Jacob, that vitamin C taken with a meal destroys the vitamin B12 in the meal. In the June 1976 issue of the *Journal of Clinical Nutrition* an article was published by Newmark and three collaborators, who had carefully repeated the work done by Herbert and Jacob, using a reliable method of analysis for vitamin B12, and had found that in fact no significant destruction of vitamin B12, is caused by vitamin C. They were able to show that Herbert and Jacob had used a thoroughly unreliable method of analysis for B12. Nevertheless, both Victor Herbert and Jean Mayer have continued to publish articles in newspapers in which the statement is made that vitamin C destroys the vitamin B12 in meals.

Even Professor John Yudkin, of the University of London, has been guilty of a failure to examine the evidence about orthomolecular medicine in an unbiased way. Yudkin is one of the best of the older nutritionists. We can be grateful to him for the extensive work that he has done on the effect of sucrose on the health of experimental animals and of human beings. The evidence that the ordinary intake of sucrose, sugar, averaging more than 100 pounds per person in the United States, England, and some other countries, is seriously harmful to health is discussed in detail in his 1972 book, *Sweet and Dangerous*, and is summarized in his new book, *This Nutrition Business*, published in 1976 by Davis-Poynter, London. In the new book, however, he devotes several pages to a discussion of megavitamin therapy. The discussion is superficial. For example, he does not mention the fact that most animals, manufacture ascorbic acid, and that the amount manufactured per day lies in the range, for different species of animals, from 2 to 20 grams, per 70 kilograms body weight. This fact is a strong argument in support of the thesis that similar amounts might well be required for optimum health in human beings. He says that, "The most spectacular claim along these lines is that schizophrenia can be improved, if not entirely cured, by the administration of two vitamins - nicotinamide and vitamin C - in doses between 100 and 1000 times as much as are usually accepted as being the normal requirement." He then states that these claims have been made repeatedly during the past few years, but have never been satisfactorily demonstrated. His discussion of what he calls the

fallacies of the arguments for orthomolecular medicine is superficial and illogical.

It is regrettable that Professor Yudkin and other authorities in the field of nutrition are not willing to take the responsibility of examining the evidence about nutrition in relation to disease in an unbiased and responsible way.

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